

R O S I A
REMOTE REHABILITATION SERVICE FOR ISOLATED AREAS

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ROSIA POSITIONING PAPER

Co-design to unlock the adoption of health apps and digital therapeutics by healthcare systems

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CONTENT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CO-DESIGN TO UNLOCK THE ADOPTION OF HEALTH APPS AND DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS BY HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS

The experience in telerehabilitation

INTEGRATING DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS INTO CLINICAL PRACTICE: THE EUROPEAN PATHWAY

Why this is important

Methodology

The four-phase adoption journey for Digital Therapeutics: from development to scale

What has been done until now?

Where we are

BARRIERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM ROSIA PROJECT

From development to adoption: systemic misalignments along the digital health journey

KEY TAKEAWAYS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ROSIA project

ROZIA is a Horizon 2020 Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) project that addressed limited access to specialized rehabilitation services, particularly in rural and depopulated areas. The project was led by its public buyers, the Servicio Aragonés de la Salud (SALUD) in Spain, the Unidade Local de Saúde de Coimbra (ULS Coimbra, formerly CHUC) in Portugal, and the National Rehabilitation Hospital (NRH) in Ireland, with the Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud (IACS) as coordinator and lead procurer. Between 2021 and 2025, it developed and validated two telerehabilitation platforms (Rehabilify and RAISE) tested over ten months across three clinical sites in Ireland, Portugal, and Spain, involving 124 patients, 36 healthcare professionals, and seven relevant pathologies.

The platforms integrated an ICT Innovation Ecosystem including a clinically prescribable catalogue, an open platform for data sharing, and a developer kit to support developers. The project demonstrates both the transformative potential and the systemic barriers facing Digital Therapeutics (DTx) in Europe.

This positioning paper synthesizes evidence from ROSIA's implementation experience, complemented by a Policy workshop with European stakeholders (December 2025), bilateral consultations, and analysis of recent initiatives including Label2Enable, ORCHA, EFPIA, and MedTech Europe.

The challenge: prescription and reimbursement

When ROSIA was designed in 2020, the consortium assumed that by 2025-2026, clear frameworks for DTx prescription and adoption would exist across Europe. This has not materialized. While the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR) harmonizes CE marking, downstream pathways for evaluation, prescription, and reimbursement vary drastically across Member States. Only a few countries have structured fast-track mechanisms (DiGA in Germany, PECAN in France, NICE in the UK, mHealthBelgium), while Spain, Portugal, and Ireland (the three ROSIA countries) lack dedicated national DTx frameworks, creating major barriers for integration into public health systems.

The four-phase adoption journey: from innovation to scale

ROZIA proposes a four-phase adoption model that captures the full journey from innovation to routine use. It begins with development and early validation, moves through regulatory approval and CE marking, continues with technical integration into clinical workflows, and culminates in scaled adoption supported by reimbursement mechanisms and sustained real-world evidence generation. A cross-cutting constraint involves ethical and competent authority approvals, which often introduce delays difficult to reconcile with rigid PCP project timelines.

Seven structural barriers identified

Analysis of ROSIA's experience and European stakeholder evidence identifies seven key barriers:

1. Overlapping regulatory frameworks (MDR, IVDR, AI Act, EHDS, Data Act, NIS2) creating legal uncertainty
2. Fragmentation of evaluation and quality frameworks, with multiple labels and schemes lacking mutual recognition

3. Inconsistent clinical evidence and HTA approaches, over-relying on randomized trials and focusing narrowly on clinical outcomes while overlooking system-level benefits
4. Weak linkage between assessment and access decisions, with 12-24 month delays from CE marking to effective prescription
5. Static governance models for dynamic software products, with unclear rules on substantial modifications
6. Digital health literacy gaps among professionals and patients, compounded by cultural resistance and digital exclusion risks
7. Single Market dysfunction, forcing CE-marked DTx to repeatedly adapt evidence packages, disproportionately affecting SMEs

Five key insights from ROSIA: integrated care requires system-level policy responses

ROSIA demonstrates that value emerges not from a single app, but from an integrated telerehabilitation ecosystem. Key insights include:

1. **Semantic interoperability:** Foundational requirement for meaningful integration of rehabilitation exercises and outcomes
2. **Motivation and behavioral engagement:** Central determinants of long-term success and broad data use.
3. **Shift in the unit of evaluation:** From individual apps to integrated systems, challenging app-centric HTA models
4. **Operational compliance gaps:** Legal principles exist, but practical tools for consent management and multi-actor data sharing remain limited
5. **PCP timeline misalignment:** Rigid deadlines vs. longer evidence generation cycles

Seven key takeaways

To address these barriers, ROSIA proposes coordinated action across seven policy domains:

1. Reduce fragmentation and uncertainty to strengthen Europe's competitiveness
2. Align policy instruments across the full adoption journey (Phases 1-4)
3. Enable system-level evaluation methodologies for integrated care solutions
4. Make semantic interoperability a strategic EU priority for digital rehabilitation and chronic care
5. Adapt PCP design to support meaningful validation and continuity beyond proof of concept
6. Operationalize data governance and compliance by design across ecosystems
7. Expand regulatory sandboxes to simplify implementation and promote coordinated learning

Conclusion

ROSIA demonstrates both the transformative potential and the systemic barriers facing Digital Therapeutics in Europe. Moving from innovation to sustainable adoption requires more than CE marking. It demands coherent governance, reusable evidence principles, semantic interoperability, lifecycle-aware evaluation, and procurement models that ensure continuity beyond pilots.

ROSIA's lessons provide actionable guidance for EU institutions and Member States seeking to accelerate integrated, digitally supported care pathways across Europe.

CO-DESIGN TO UNLOCK THE ADOPTION OF HEALTH APPS AND DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS BY HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS

The experience in telerehabilitation

ROSIA is a Precommercial Procurement Project, funded by the EC under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017606. ROSIA ran from January 2021 to December 2025.

During the project, two pilot platforms were developed: the [Rehabilify](#) platform, developed by the consortium led by Eurecat (Spain), and the [RAISE](#) platform, developed by the consortium led by Ethniko Kentro (Greece). These platforms were tested in a real environment in the three sites of the project: Ireland, Portugal and Spain during 10 months. The testing involved 124 patients, 36 healthcare professionals, and targeted 7 pathologies. This piloting allowed the co-creation with clinicians and patients, and also allowed to address the challenge of complying with procedures and requirements of three different healthcare systems.

ROSIA addressed the lack of accessible rehabilitation services for patients living in depopulated and remote areas, where long travel distances to specialised centres often hindered continuity of care and the completion of rehabilitation programmes.

The project leveraged advanced digital technologies to deliver supervised telerehabilitation, enabling patients to continue rehabilitation closer to home and for longer periods. ROSIA focused on seven clinical conditions requiring long-term rehabilitation: chronic spinal cord injury, acquired brain injury, COPD, arthroplasty, cardiovascular diseases, hip fracture and COVID-19.

To support clinical adoption, ROSIA developed an ICT Innovation Ecosystem for telerehabilitation composed of three main elements: a clinically prescribable catalogue integrating third-party digital rehabilitation solutions, an OPEN Platform enabling data sharing and system integration, and a Developer Software Kit (DSK) to facilitate the development of an ecosystem of developers able to foster innovation for broader range of pathologies.

ROSIA highlighted that telerehabilitation value does not lie in a single app, but in an integrated ecosystem of devices, clinical pathways and interoperable digital services. This shift from app based solutions to system level care models has major implications for evaluation, governance and adoption.

The project was structured around four core work areas: an integrated care model ensuring continuity of care, the adoption of high-tech telerehabilitation solutions, enhanced patient experience, and a value-based model enabling a sustainable business model.

ROSIA implemented a Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) approach to develop and validate solutions not previously available on the market. Five suppliers competed across three PCP phases, with two final solutions validated in real clinical settings across three European regions. Solution development was jointly funded by public healthcare authorities from Spain (Servicio Aragonés de Salud), Portugal (Unidade Local de Saúde de Coimbra) and Ireland (National Rehabilitation Hospital), with the Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud (IACS) acting as coordinator and lead procurer.

Beyond its specific focus on telerehabilitation, ROSIA offers a broader lens on one of the main systemic challenges facing Digital Therapeutics in Europe: the gap between technological innovation and routine health system adoption. The project demonstrates that while regulatory pathways such as CE marking are necessary, they remain insufficient to ensure prescription, reimbursement, interoperability and sustainable integration into clinical practice. As such, ROSIA can be seen as a testbed for understanding the structural conditions required to scale integrated digital care solutions across Member States.

When the ROSIA PCP consortium designed this approach in 2020, it did so in the context of a rapidly evolving digital health landscape, with the explicit understanding that the large-scale deployment of telerehabilitation services would ultimately depend (among other potential barriers) on the resolution of regulatory, evaluation, prescription and reimbursement frameworks for Health Apps and Digital Therapeutics. The consortium therefore assumed that, by the time the solutions reached deployment readiness, sufficient progress would have been achieved at national and European level to enable their systematic clinical prescription and adoption. However, as of 2026, this assumption has not materialised. Across the countries represented in the ROSIA consortium and in much of Europe more broadly, the regulatory and operational conditions for the prescription of Digital Therapeutics remain uneven, fragmented or insufficiently defined. This persisting gap underscores the need to revisit and analyse the prescription pathway in greater depth as a critical enabler for the sustainable adoption of Digital Therapeutics within public healthcare systems.

This positioning paper therefore distils the key barriers and policy lessons emerging from ROSIA, with the aim of informing EU level efforts to strengthen coherent adoption pathways for Digital Therapeutics and complex rehabilitation ecosystems.

Integrating digital therapeutics into clinical practice: the European pathway

Within the broader landscape of digital health technologies, **health apps and digital therapeutics (DTx) represent distinct categories that differ fundamentally** in terms of clinical intent, regulatory requirements and system integration (see Figure 1). Health apps are generally oriented towards wellness, prevention or self-management and are subject to limited regulatory oversight, with minimal alignment with formal clinical workflows. In contrast, Digital Therapeutics (DTx) are clinically validated, evidence-based software interventions (standalone or combined with hardware) designed to prevent, manage or treat medical conditions. As such, DTxs require formal regulatory certification, clearly defined prescription and monitoring frameworks, and full integration into health information systems.

This positioning paper focuses primarily on DTx, as they represent the category requiring systematic integration into publicly funded healthcare systems and facing the most significant adoption barriers related to prescription, reimbursement and regulatory pathways.

From a health policy perspective, DTx represents a potentially significant lever to improve health outcomes, enhance system efficiency and support more personalised models of care. However, despite their increasing clinical maturity, the regulatory, evaluation, prescription and reimbursement frameworks for DTx across Europe remain fragmented and, in many cases, insufficiently defined. This lack of

harmonisation constitutes a major barrier to their systematic adoption within publicly funded healthcare systems.

The integration of Health Apps and Digital Therapeutics into public health information systems raises two broad categories of challenges that need to be addressed in parallel:

- 1) On the one hand, there are regulatory issues related to the certification, validation and prescription of these solutions, including their clinical evidence, safety, and reimbursement frameworks.
- 2) On the other hand, effective integration requires robust interoperability with existing health information systems, enabling the structured incorporation of patient-generated data into clinicians' dashboards, EHRs, and decision-support tools. This implies a reorganisation of existing care pathways, clarifying roles and responsibilities, adapting clinical workflows, and ensuring that digital solutions genuinely support, rather than fragment, continuity of care.

The responsibility for the regulatory dimension of Health Apps and DTx (including their certification, clinical validation and prescription) lies primarily with public authorities at regional, national and European level. Regulatory agencies, health technology assessment (HTA) bodies and payers

are key actors in defining approval pathways, evidence requirements and reimbursement conditions. In parallel, professional bodies and clinical societies contribute by developing clinical guidelines and prescribing criteria, helping to ensure consistent, safe and appropriate use of Digital Therapeutics within healthcare systems.

ROSIA addresses the second challenge (interoperability/integration) through a pre-commercial procurement approach focused on building an enabling digital infrastructure for telerehabilitation services. Rather than promoting individual stand-alone solutions, ROSIA supports the development of a modular ecosystem that allows third-party technologies to be technically and operationally integrated into a structured framework for clinical use. Central to this approach is a curated environment that facilitates the prescription of interoperable digital solutions by care teams, while ensuring secure data exchange and alignment with existing clinical workflows. This ecosystem is underpinned by shared digital services for data management and interoperability, as well as dedicated technical interfaces that support developers in adapting their solutions to heterogeneous regional health IT infrastructures. In doing so, ROSIA addresses practical barriers to system integration and scalability, while creating a controlled setting in which innovation can be aligned with public healthcare requirements.

Digital health

Technologies that use digital tools, data, software, or connectivity to improve health, healthcare delivery, or health-related behaviours

- Telehealth and telemedicine
- Health information systems
- AI for health

Health apps

Not regulated as medical devices

- Wellness and fitness apps
- Meditation apps
- Self-management apps

Digital medicine

Evidence-based digital technologies that measure, diagnose, or intervene in human health, and are used in clinical care or research

- Digital diagnosis, digital biomarkers, remote monitoring

Digital therapeutics (DTx)

Evidence-based, clinically validated software interventions that prevent, manage, or treat a medical condition or disease

- **Standalone DTx:** works independently
- **Companion DTx:** supports or enhances the use of a drug or medical treatment
- **Combination DTx:** inseparably paired with a drug or device

Figure 1. Types of digital health technologies¹

Why this is important

Healthcare systems are facing a growing risk of structural unsustainability driven by demographic ageing, the rising prevalence of chronic diseases, shortages of healthcare professionals and increasing expenditure. **Chronic conditions already account for the majority of healthcare spending**, largely due to their long-term nature and reliance on repeated, resource intensive interactions with the healthcare system.

Traditional models of care, designed around acute and episodic interventions, are poorly adapted to managing chronic patients efficiently at scale, resulting in avoidable hospitalisations, fragmented care pathways and escalating costs.

Advanced digitalisation, including digital health applications and Digital Therapeutics, offers an opportunity to move beyond reactive medicine towards more continuous, proactive and

personalised models of care. By supporting self-management, improving adherence and enabling earlier intervention, these solutions can alleviate pressure on healthcare professionals while contributing to more efficient use of resources. ROSIA illustrates this potential particularly clearly in telerehabilitation, where continuity of care and sustained patient engagement are essential for long term outcomes.

From the patient perspective, insufficient adoption of digitally enabled care models risks worsening outcomes and quality of life.

Without continuous support tools that facilitate adherence and engagement, patients with chronic conditions are more likely to experience poor disease control, avoidable complications and reduced treatment effectiveness. Digitally

¹ Own creation based on EFPIA. Improving access to Digital Therapeutics in Europe [Internet]. Brussels: EFPIA; 2023 Jun. Available at: <https://www.efpia.eu/media/677347/improving-access-to-digital-therapeutics-in-europe.pdf>

supported pathways can therefore play a critical role in improving patient experience and long term management.

From the perspective of the European digital health industry, limited adoption also represents a systemic competitiveness risk. Despite substantial public investment in innovation, European SMEs developing DTx remain

dependent on effective demand from healthcare systems. When prescription, reimbursement and scaling pathways are fragmented or slow to materialise, innovation struggles to translate into sustainable business models and real world impact. Over time, this dynamic risks weakening Europe’s digital health ecosystem, discouraging investment and undermining leadership in integrated digital care solutions.

Methodology

Structured search and literature review

Several papers, including white papers and policy papers, have been consulted to elaborate the state of the art and to explore the perspectives of different stakeholders, such as: MedTech, Lable2Enable, EFPIA, RedETS and AQuAS, EIT Health...See BIBLIOGRAPHY for the comprehensive list of articles consulted.

ROSIA policy workshop

On the 2nd of December, 2025, a Policy Workshop organized by the ROSIA project was held. Its main topic was the evaluation, prescription and reimbursement of DTx. The twelve participants, among which were representatives from the European Commission,

MedTech Europe, EHTEL, ORCHA, EFPIA, EIT Health and HIPPS project, were very knowledgeable about the topic of interest, which allowed a productive discussion.

Bilateral meetings

The Policy Workshop was followed by a series of bilateral meetings with some of the participants, and other stakeholders. Eight people participated in these sessions (see ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS, page 20).

These interactions lead to messages, conclusions and insights that are integrated in the content of next sections.

The four-phase adoption journey for Digital Therapeutics: from development to scale

To capture the challenges identified through ROSIA, this positioning paper proposes a four-phase model (see Figure 2) describing the systemic pathway that DTx must navigate in order to move from innovation to routine healthcare adoption. The model illustrates that scaling is not achieved through regulatory approval alone, but requires alignment across evidence generation, integration capacity and access mechanisms.

Phase 1 focuses on development and early validation, where solutions define their intended clinical use, establish usability with patients and

professionals, and generate initial evidence to support their medical claim.

Phase 2 centres on regulatory approval, ensuring compliance with the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR) and enabling CE marking as the gateway for market entry.

Phase 3 addresses technical and operational integration, where interoperability, workflow alignment, clinical oversight and organisational readiness determine if solutions can be developed within real healthcare environments.

Phase 4 concerns adoption at scale, requiring structured prescription and reimbursement pathways, sustained real-world evidence generation, and the embedding of Digital Therapeutics into care pathways over time.

Across all phases, ethical and competent authority approvals represent a cross-cutting constraint, often introducing delays that are difficult to reconcile with rigid innovation procurement timelines. ROSIA therefore highlights that while CE marking is necessary, it remains insufficient: scalable adoption depends on coordinated

governance, integration infrastructures and coherent access conditions beyond regulation alone.

In summary, the four phases reflect the progression from early validation, to regulatory clearance, to integration in care delivery, and finally to reimbursement-supported adoption at scale.

Figure 2. Four-phase adoption journey for digital therapeutics

What has been done until now?

Over the past decade, the European Union has progressively built a regulatory and policy framework to address the evaluation, safety and adoption of mobile health applications and digital health solutions. Early initiatives included the **2013–2014 Green Paper on Mobile Health**, led by DG CONNECT in collaboration with DG SANTE, which identified key challenges such as legal uncertainty, lack of evidence, data protection and interoperability. This was followed in 2014 by **voluntary mHealth Assessment Guidelines**, developed with Member States and stakeholders, establishing baseline criteria for safety, privacy and clinical validity. In parallel, the EU introduced horizontal regulatory instruments with significant implications for digital health, notably the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, applied from 2018, which imposed strict requirements on the

processing of health data, consent, data protection impact assessments and cross-border data transfers for Health Apps.

From a product safety and conformity perspective, the adoption of the **Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745)** and the **In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation (IVDR 2017/746)** marked a major regulatory shift. Fully applicable from 2021 and 2022 respectively, these regulations clarified that many diagnostic and therapeutic Health Apps fall under medical device legislation, introducing risk-based classification, mandatory CE marking, strengthened clinical evidence requirements and enhanced post-market surveillance obligation. More recently, the publication of the **AI Act** in 2024, has added a further regulatory layer, classifying many

AI-enabled health applications as high-risk systems and introducing additional requirements related to transparency, validation, human oversight and risk management, with overlaps and interactions with existing medical device rules.

Alongside binding regulation, the European Commission has supported multiple EU-funded **initiatives and coordination mechanisms** to operationalise quality assessment and validation. Projects such as the **EU mHealth Hub and Digital Health Europe (DHE)** developed common quality frameworks, testing infrastructures and interoperability support for digital health solutions. The Label2Enable project (Horizon

2020, 2019–2022) further contributed by developing a quality labelling framework focused on trustworthiness, accessibility and transparency, including self-assessment tools for developers and pilot activities with app stores and payers. At governance level, coordination has been reinforced through bodies such as the **Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG)**, which issues guidance on medical device software qualification and clinical evaluation, and the eHealth Network, which aligns national eHealth strategies, supports cross-border services and contributes to the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Where we are

Regarding the regulatory aspects, there is a governing regulation that all DTx must follow, which is the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR), that, after a positive assessment, allows it to obtain the CE marking. This procedure is unified and equal for all Member States.

The divergence appears when it comes to the evaluation that a DTx undergoes after the CE-marking. This evaluation, also known as health technology assessment (HTA), is performed at the national/regional/local level, and stipulates which DTx are suitable for being prescribed and reimbursed.

There are several EU countries that have an established pathway for the evaluation of DTx:

Germany through DiGA, France through PECAN, Belgium through mHealthBelgium, and United

Kingdom through EVA (Early Value Assessment). The objective of these tools is to assess whether a DTx delivers value compared to the standard of care, and provide a temporary trial period during which evidence can be gathered to achieve adoption and reimbursement by healthcare systems. The way these tools work is by including the evaluated DTx into catalogues or directories that clinicians can access.

The following table (Table 1) summarizes the characteristics and requirements for prescription of the existing fast-track processes.

Table 1. Existing directories of DTx that have been evaluated and are suitable for prescription and reimbursement

COUNTRY	Prescription process	Key requirements for prescription	Apps in catalogue	Starting year	Link
Germany (DiGA) 	After CE marking and BfArM approval, the app is listed in the DiGA directory. Physicians and psychotherapists prescribe via e-prescription; patients receive an activation code to download and use the app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE marking under MDR -Positive health effects (clinical evidence) -Data protection compliance (GDPR) -Interoperability and usability standards 	~60 apps	2019	DiGA Directory
France (PECAN) 	DMN approved under PECAN can be prescribed by healthcare professionals during early reimbursement phase; integrated into chronic disease programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE marking - Initial clinical evidence of benefit -Cybersecurity and interoperability compliance 	~3 apps reimbursed; 23 pending	2023	HAS-SANTÉ
United Kingdom (NICE EVA / ESF) 	NICE-recommended technologies are integrated into NHS formularies; clinicians prescribe as part of care pathways, supported by NHS trusts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clinical effectiveness evidence - Cost-effectiveness analysis - Compliance with DTAC (Digital Technology Assessment Criteria) - CE or UKCA marking 	100+ digital health solutions (40+ DTx)	2019 (ESF), 2022 (EVA)	NICE Digital Health
Belgium (mHealthBelgium) 	Apps validated at Level 3+ are included in reimbursement schemes; physicians prescribe within hospital agreements for chronic disease management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE marking -Secure connectivity -Proof of socio-economic value - Compliance with interoperability standards 	~41 apps validated	2018	mHealthBelgium

Regarding the **specific situation of the countries participating in ROSIA** (Spain, Ireland and Portugal), all three lack a specific evaluation framework for DTx, but there are emerging initiatives:

SPAIN

In Spain, prescription of DTx is possible but not standardized. Without an established public reimbursement model, access depends on private payment or pilot programs. Nonetheless, two initiatives are changing this situation:

- The Spanish Network of Health Technology Assessment Agencies (RedETS) has adapted HTA methodologies for digital health technologies. However, these guidelines are still in early stages and not yet operational for systematic DTx adoption.
- The Consorcio DTx was created with the aim of advancing the evaluation of DTx and facilitating their access to the Spanish healthcare products market. It is a strategic alliance between the pharmaceutical industry, scientific societies, start-ups, and public institutions

IRELAND

In Ireland, the HTA is managed by the Health Information and Quality Authority (HIQA), but current processes are designed for traditional medical devices, and are not agile enough for digital solutions and telerehabilitation. The Digital for Care Framework (2024–2030) sets a roadmap for digital transformation, but does not yet include specific pathways for DTx integration.

PORTUGAL

In this case, INFARMED oversees health technology evaluation through the SiNATS system, but, again, current frameworks do not address iterative software updates or agile evidence generation.

As stated in a recent white paper on DiGA in Portugal, conducted by EIT Health, Portugal currently lacks a national reimbursement framework for DTx, relying instead on fragmented processes across public and private sectors. In the public system, reimbursement requires a prescription from a National Health Service (SNS) doctor, but only two solutions are subsidized: a free telemonitoring app (*Telemonit SNS 24*) and the FreeStyle Libre glucose monitor with partial copayment. A “Social Prescription” program was introduced in 2024 to fund activities promoting mental health and well-being. In the private sector, access depends on out-of-pocket payments or agreements with insurers.

Portugal is considered a ‘certifier’, prioritizing certification over direct reimbursement, which limits adoption. Key challenges include cultural resistance to value-based care, a fragmented ecosystem, gaps in digital health literacy among professionals, complex regulatory pathways without a clear framework, and insufficient digital infrastructure and interoperability. Despite these barriers, initiatives such as funding programs, test beds, and innovation hubs aim to accelerate digital health integration.

Barriers and recommendations

This analysis draws on recent European policy initiatives, industry position papers, stakeholder inputs and empirical evidence to identify the main barriers to the prescription, reimbursement and large-scale adoption of Health Apps and DTx in Europe. Insights from ROSIA's implementation experience are complemented by evidence from Label2Enable, ORCHA's operational evaluation practice, EFPIA and MedTech Europe analyses, and discussions held during the ROSIA Policy Workshop and bilateral consultations.

Together, these sources highlight seven structural barriers that continue to limit scalable and sustainable adoption across Member States.

1. Fragmented and incoherent governance framework for digital health technologies

Current situation

Health apps and Digital Therapeutics are simultaneously subject to sector-specific legislation (MDR/IVDR) and multiple horizontal digital acts (AI Act, EHDS, Data Act, NIS2 and cybersecurity legislation). The cumulative and overlapping nature of these frameworks creates legal uncertainty, fragmented accountability and inconsistent obligations across Member States. This undermines predictability for innovators and authorities alike, increases compliance complexity, and risks renewed Single Market fragmentation through divergent national implementation.

Recommendation

Europe's ability to scale Digital Therapeutics depends on reducing systemic uncertainty and ensuring coherent implementation across regulatory instruments. EU-level guidance should clarify interactions between MDR obligations and horizontal digital legislation, preventing inconsistent national interpretations and supporting a more predictable environment for innovators and healthcare systems.

2. Fragmentation of evaluation, quality and trust frameworks across Europe

Current situation

Despite increasing policy attention, evaluation and quality assurance frameworks remain fragmented. Multiple labels, assessment schemes and directories coexist, applying heterogeneous criteria for quality, safety, usability, data protection and evidence. This fragmentation leads to duplication of assessments, limited reuse of results and low mutual recognition, undermining trust and increasing administrative burden for innovators.

Recommendation

Establish a harmonised European quality baseline grounded in CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2, as proposed by Label2Enable. Enable incremental and cross-country recognition of prior evaluations, allowing evidence generated in one Member State to be reused elsewhere rather than regenerated. Predictable and portable assessment outputs would strengthen trust while reducing duplication across jurisdictions.

3. Inconsistent and non-transferable approaches to clinical evidence, value assessment and HTA for digital health technologies

Current situation

While Barrier 2 concerns baseline quality and trust assessment, this barrier relates specifically to reimbursement-relevant evidence generation and health technology assessment (HTA). Current frameworks remain largely app-centric and vary significantly across countries, with limited alignment on methodologies, endpoints, comparators and reporting standards.

A central challenge is that clinical evidence generated for one national pathway is rarely transferable to others. Even after CE marking, innovators often need to adapt study designs, endpoints and economic evidence repeatedly to meet divergent national HTA expectations, creating duplication and delaying reimbursement decisions across jurisdictions.

Assessment processes also continue to rely predominantly on randomised controlled trials, despite growing recognition of the complementary role of real-world evidence (RWE) in capturing the iterative, context-dependent and evolving nature of software-based interventions.

Illustrative examples (from the ROSIA policy workshop).

National fast-track schemes apply divergent criteria. Germany's DiGA recognises both clinical outcomes and structural improvements with broad methodological flexibility, while France's PECAN places greater emphasis on clinical benefit and cybersecurity. Belgium's mHealthBelgium introduces socio-economic value assessment, yet standardisation of cost–benefit criteria remains insufficient.

Recommendation

Promote greater alignment of principles for clinical evidence generation, documentation and reporting, explicitly recognising the role of RWE alongside randomised trials. Greater convergence of HTA expectations would enable more reusable evidence packages across Member States, reducing duplication and supporting faster, more predictable access decisions.

4. Weak linkage between assessment, HTA, evidence and downstream access decisions

Current situation

Even where evaluations and HTA-relevant evidence exist, they frequently remain disconnected from prescription, reimbursement and routine use. Unclear roles in the evaluation process (particularly the distinction between company-driven, “push”, and payer-driven, “pull”, models) further exacerbate this disconnect. ORCHA plays a distinct role by translating technical evaluation outputs into operationally usable information for clinicians, managers and procurement bodies.

Illustrative examples (from the ROSIA policy workshop):

CE marking represents only the starting point. While DiGA listing may be reached within months, the overall time from CE marking to effective prescription frequently exceeds 12–24 months once additional evidence generation and price negotiations are included. In several countries, solutions remain indefinitely in provisional phases without achieving permanent reimbursement.

Recommendation

Establish explicit and structured bridges between assessment, HTA and access decisions. This includes HTA-relevant outputs consumable by payers, operational mechanisms embedding evaluation into deployable catalogues and formularies, and clearer national prescription and reimbursement pathways informed by aligned European principles.

5. Governance models that do not reflect the dynamic lifecycle of digital products

Current situation

Digital health technologies evolve continuously through software updates, algorithmic changes and data-driven learning. Existing governance, assessment and HTA mechanisms often remain static, with unclear rules on what constitutes substantial modification and when reassessment is required. Continuous post-deployment monitoring is essential to ensure evaluated solutions remain safe, appropriate and aligned with their intended use.

Illustrative examples (from the ROSIA policy workshop):

Several stakeholders also pointed to the need for provisional access and accelerated coverage mechanisms, allowing early deployment while fit-for-purpose evidence is generated under controlled conditions.

Recommendation

Implement lifecycle-aware governance with clearer, harmonised guidance on updates, substantial modifications and reassessment triggers. Expand regulatory sandboxes and supervised testing environments to enable early deployment and iterative improvement, allowing governance, HTA and access requirements to evolve in parallel with product maturity.

6. Insufficient digital health literacy and organisational readiness for adoption

Current situation

Even where governance frameworks, evaluation schemes and access pathways exist, insufficient digital health literacy and limited organisational readiness remain significant barriers. Lack of systematic integration into clinical pathways and guidelines, combined with low digital literacy among healthcare professionals and patients, hinders uptake and effective use. These challenges are compounded by cultural resistance and digital exclusion risks, particularly among older populations and in rural settings.

Recommendation

Implement structured education, training and change-management initiatives targeting both healthcare professionals and patients. These should foster confidence and trust in digital solutions, support integration into routine care pathways, and ensure equitable access across regions and populations.

7. Limited scalability, predictability and effective functioning of the Single Market

Current situation

Even after CE marking, innovators (particularly SMEs) continue to face repeated national evidence requirements, divergent access conditions and limited portability of assessment outputs. A single digital therapeutic often needs to adapt endpoints, study designs, usability data and economic models when entering different markets, delaying deployment and increasing costs.

Illustrative examples (from the ROSIA policy workshop):

Participants noted that this duplication of effort disproportionately affects startups and SMEs, slowing cross-border uptake and undermining Europe's capacity to scale digital health innovation.

Recommendation

Priority should be given to cross-country reuse of evidence packages and greater mutual recognition of prior assessments. More predictable and SME-friendly access pathways would reduce duplication, lower scaling costs and enable sustainable deployment of Digital Therapeutics across Member States.

Insights and recommendations from ROSIA project

ROSIA provides a distinctive case study for understanding the challenges of deploying complex digital health solutions within European healthcare systems. Rather than focusing on a single application, ROSIA addresses telerehabilitation through an integrated ecosystem combining heterogeneous devices, digital solutions, clinical workflows, and data flows within reconfigured care pathways. This level of ambition exposes structural insights that extend beyond project-specific implementation and reflect broader challenges affecting the digital transformation of healthcare in Europe.

The following five insights, derived from ROSIA's design and implementation, illustrate how current approaches to

interoperability, data governance, evaluation, evidence generation, and innovation procurement struggle to accommodate complex, system-level digital

health interventions. These provide critical considerations for future policy design aimed at supporting integrated care models.

INSIGHT 1 – SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY AS A PREREQUISITE FOR SYSTEM-LEVEL DIGITAL CARE

ROSIA highlights that complex digital health interventions cannot be effectively deployed without a shared semantic interoperability layer. There is no common "shared language" enabling different rehabilitation technologies to communicate and be understood consistently.

Integrating heterogeneous devices and digital solutions (ranging from sensors and exercise-based applications to decision-support and recommendation functionalities) requires more than technical connectivity. Meaningful clinical integration depends on the ability to

consistently interpret exercises, functional outcomes, and device-generated data across solutions.

Clinicians need to retain control over therapeutic decisions, including exercise selection and the type and granularity of data used for follow-up, within established care pathways and clinical dashboards. However, the absence of shared taxonomies and semantic reference models for digital rehabilitation limits interoperability at system level, constraining integration, evaluation, and scalability.

This insight underscores that semantic interoperability is not a technical detail, but a foundational enabler for integrated digital care.

INSIGHT 2 – MOTIVATION AND BEHAVIOURAL DIMENSIONS ARE CENTRAL TO COMPLEX DIGITAL HEALTH INTERVENTIONS

Complex health challenges such as telerehabilitation cannot be effectively addressed through isolated functional components alone. Patient motivation and sustained engagement are critical determinants of outcomes, particularly in long-term and behaviour-dependent interventions.

Enabling effective motivational strategies requires access to a broader range of patient-related data beyond exercise performance or disease-specific clinical parameters, including behavioural, contextual, and longitudinal information.

This illustrates why the next phase of healthcare digitalisation increasingly

depends on the availability of a wide spectrum of data capable of supporting personalised, adaptive, and patient-centred interventions, while ensuring such data are collected and shared in a compliant and trustworthy manner.

INSIGHT 3 – THE UNIT OF EVALUATION SHIFTS FROM APPS TO INTEGRATED SYSTEMS

In complex digital health ecosystems, value no longer emerges at the level of individual apps but at the level of integrated systems combining technologies, professionals, and organisational processes within care pathways. App-centric evaluation frameworks therefore struggle to capture the real-world impact of such interventions and provide limited support for HTA, reimbursement, and scaling decisions.

ROSIA highlights the need to reconsider the appropriate unit of evaluation, moving towards system-level assessment approaches that reflect how digital health solutions are deployed and used in practice, particularly in integrated care settings.

INSIGHT 4 – THE OPERATIONAL COMPLIANCE GAP FOR DATA SHARING IN COMPLEX ECOSYSTEMS

Delivering integrated digital care increasingly requires access to personal data beyond traditional vital signs,

data beyond traditional vital signs, particularly when advanced DTx or AI-enabled applications are involved. While European regulation establishes clear principles for consent, revocation, purpose limitation, and accountability, stakeholders

consistently report the absence of operational, user-friendly tools that enable compliant data sharing across multi-actor ecosystems.

This operational compliance gap creates friction between regulatory requirements and real-world deployment, limiting the ability of healthcare systems to fully leverage data-driven digital care while maintaining trust and legal certainty.

INSIGHT 5 – MISALIGNMENT BETWEEN PCP TIMELINES, EVIDENCE GENERATION AND CONTINUITY

Experience from ROSIA highlighted a critical misalignment between rigid PCP deadlines and the practical requirements of clinical validation, recruitment, ethical approvals,

and meaningful evidence generation. Significant effort is often required to address integration and governance challenges before data collection can begin, compressing pilot phases into limited proof-of-concept exercises.

As continuity after a PCP is frequently linked to evidence of value, the absence of shared value definitions and insufficient time for data generation place both buyers and contractors at risk of losing opportunities for follow-on procurement.

This dynamic increases the likelihood of lost public value and undermines the effectiveness of PCPs as instruments for sustainable adoption in complex innovation contexts.

From development to adoption: systemic misalignments along the digital health journey

The barriers identified in the previous section do not operate in isolation. Rather, they emerge and reinforce one another across the four phase adoption journey, creating cumulative challenges that undermine the transition from innovation to sustainable adoption.

In **Phase 1** (Development), early design choices driven by regulatory feasibility may overlook downstream adoption requirements. ROSIA illustrates this: telerehabilitation solutions were initially designed around technical validation, without yet fully capturing the behavioural engagement, workflow integration and evidence requirements that would later determine their deployability in real care pathways.

In **Phase 2** (Regulatory approval), while CE marking ensures safety and compliance, it does not address operational deployment challenges. As highlighted in Insight 5, the operational compliance gap for multi actor data sharing becomes particularly visible here, where legal requirements exist but practical tools remain limited.

In **Phase 3** (Technical integration), semantic interoperability emerges as the critical bottleneck (Insight 1). ROSIA demonstrates that without shared taxonomies for rehabilitation exercises and outcomes, even technically interoperable solutions struggle to integrate meaningfully into clinical dashboards and decision support systems.

In **Phase 4** (Adoption at scale), misalignments converge. Evidence generated in pilots often proves insufficient for national reimbursement criteria. The PCP timeline challenge (Insight 6) also becomes acute, as rigid project deadlines conflict with the extended periods required for ethical approvals, recruitment and meaningful evidence generation. This creates a risk that solutions remain proof of concept exercises without a clear pathway to scale.

What ROSIA reveals about adoption and integrated care policy

Taken together, these observations suggest that the adoption of Health Apps and Digital Therapeutics and complex digital health solutions should be understood as a systemic process rather than a sequence of independent gates. ROSIA illustrates how failures to align design, regulation, integration and procurement across the four phases undermine the transition towards integrated, digitally supported care models.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

Policy messages to enable the adoption and scaling of integrated digital care in Europe

Key takeaway 1 - Strategic urgency and competitiveness

Europe's ability to scale Digital Therapeutics depends on reducing systemic uncertainty and avoiding a regulatory and market environment that disadvantages European innovators compared to other global regions.

Key takeaway 2 – Coherence across the full adoption pathway

Beyond CE marking, adoption requires coordinated policy alignment across the entire journey from development and validation to integration, prescription and reimbursement, ensuring continuity from Phase 1 to Phase 4.

Key takeaway 3 – System level evaluation beyond app based models

Integrated digital care solutions such as telerehabilitation ecosystems require evaluation frameworks that move beyond single app assessments, capturing system level outcomes including workflow impact, care coordination and patient empowerment.

Key takeaway 4 – Semantic interoperability as enabling infrastructure

Meaningful deployment at scale depends on shared semantic interoperability frameworks, enabling rehabilitation data, exercises and outcomes to be interpreted consistently across heterogeneous solutions and clinical settings.

Key takeaway 5 – Flexible procurement pathways to bridge pilots and adoption

PCP and procurement instruments should incorporate greater flexibility and adaptive follow-on mechanisms, enabling solutions to transition smoothly from pilot validation to routine deployment without losing continuity between proof of concept and real world uptake.

Key takeaway 6 – Operationalising trustworthy data governance

Europe must strengthen practical tools for consent management, lawful multi actor data sharing and compliance by design, translating high level legal principles into operational enablers for integrated ecosystems.

Key takeaway 7 – Sandboxes as delivery mechanisms for implementation learning

Regulatory sandboxes can provide supervised environments to test compliance, interoperability and evidence generation in practice, accelerating coordinated learning and supporting smoother transition from pilots to scale.

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